

Data Distribution of Ppinaster

#Sequences

0 5,000 10,000 15,000 20,000 25,000 30,000 35,000 40,000 45,000 50,000 55,000 60,000

GO Mapping Distribution [Ppinaster]

Annotation Distribution [Ppinaster]

